

Extending social life cycle assessment to capture technological change: A case study in AI-driven laser manufacturing for the aerospace sector

Ricardo Mejía-Marchena^{a,b}, José Osorio-Tejada^a, Alejandro Domínguez-Núñez^c, Volker Hessel^{a,d,*}

^a School of Engineering, University of Warwick, Coventry, CV4 7AL, United Kingdom

^b Instituto de Estudios Hidráulicos y Ambientales (IDEHA), Departamento de Ingeniería Civil y Ambiental. Universidad del Norte, Carrera 30 - Corredor Universitario, Barranquilla, Atlántico Department, 081007, Colombia

^c R&D Department, Sofitec. Calle Juan Olivert (P.E. Aeronautico Aeropolis) 38, LA Rinconada (Sevilla), 41309, Spain

^d School of Chemical Engineering, Adelaide University, Adelaide, 5005, Australia

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ABSTRACT

This study addresses a limitation in Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA): its reliance on value chain actors, which limits the detection of social impacts from technological changes in the core processes when supply chains are largely intact. We propose an improved approach capable of evaluating emerging technologies and their interactions with social systems. This is tested in the aeronautics sector as the first S-LCA of an industrial system integrating ultrashort-pulsed laser (USPL) technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and robotics. The approach aligns with the UNEP, 2009 Guidelines and ISO 14075:2024, integrating multi-level inventory data. A new Hotspot approach identifies relevant subcategories. The impact assessment uses benchmark-based scoring with stakeholder weighting, and sensitivity analyses test the robustness of conditional scoring adjustments (*a*-values) and stage weightings. Under the defined scenarios, the AI-driven USPL process achieved higher social performance scores than the manual sanding in 14 of 21 social subcategories. The conditional scoring adjustments reflect the social implications, though they are based on evidence-informed assumptions; consistent results across weighting scenarios strengthen the findings. The improved S-LCA framework captures internal shifts and acts as a proactive planning and decision-support tool. It shows how emerging technologies support socially responsible industrial transitions and stakeholder-informed decisions.

1. Introduction

S-LCA is an emerging methodology supplementing Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) (Traverso et al., 2024). This assessment evaluates the social and socio-economic impacts of products, processes, or services throughout their life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal (Wang et al., 2022; Tragnone et al., 2023). Unlike LCA, which primarily focuses on environmental impacts, S-LCA examines the human and social aspects related to various stakeholders (Traverso et al., 2024). These stakeholders include workers, local communities, consumers, value chain actors, society, and children, where positive and negative social impacts are considered (Muller et al., 2021). This methodology provides a framework for recognising social risks, maintaining ethics, and promoting sustainability across global supply chains (Silva et al., 2024; Borri et al., 2024).

In 2009, the United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) and the Society of Environmental Toxicology and Chemistry (SETAC) released the initial Guidelines for the S-LCA (UNEP and SETAC, 2009), inspired by the methodological structure of the International Organisation for Standardisation (ISO) 14040:2006 (BSI and ISO, 2020). Several LCA practitioners have suggested improvements to enhance their relevance in practical situations (Tokede and Traverso, 2020). Consequently, a revised edition was released, which will be referred to as the *Guidelines moving forward* (UNEP, 2020). More recently, the ISO 14075:2024 has been published, providing an official international standard (BSI and ISO, 2024). This new standard improves consistency, but no widely accepted method for impact assessment exists (Zira et al., 2020).

According to the *guidelines*, the social life cycle impact assessment (S-LCIA) can be conducted using two distinct approaches: Type I, which

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: volker.hessel@adelaide.edu.au (V. Hessel).

uses a reference scale, and Type II, which uses an impact pathway. The first approach measures inventory indicators against a reference value and scores them based on a predefined scale. The second approach characterises the value of social inventory using specific characterisation factors (UNEP, 2020). Both approaches exhibit notable gaps that hinder their adoption. Type I, the most widely used approach in case study applications, suffers from subjectivity and inconsistent reference scales (Mármol et al., 2023). Meanwhile, Type II is limited by a lack of clear cause-and-effect links, scarce, inaccessible data, and complex social impact modelling (Lobsiger-Kägi et al., 2018).

The Social Hotspot Analysis, the first step, identifies social risks when primary data isn't available, focusing on countries and sectors for impact category selection (Pucciarelli et al., 2021; Traverso et al., 2024). However, there is currently no widely accepted method (Singh and Gupta, 2018; Michaliszyn-Gabryś et al., 2024). When choosing and applying specific indicators for these categories, it is recommended to follow the *methodological sheets*, which provide detailed guidance on selecting, defining, and implementing each indicator to ensure consistency and best practice by providing more than 100 inventory indicators (UNEP, 2021; Naghshineh et al., 2020). On the other hand, a key gap in current S-LCA frameworks is their limited ability to capture social performance changes driven by internal technological changes. These include implementing new technologies or operational changes that might have social implications, without significantly altering the external supply chain. Traditional S-LCA approaches may not capture these shifts in social performance, as their indicators and databases are not designed to evaluate technological differences within the same actor. While some S-LCA have been conducted for technology assessments, they often do not align with the *Guidelines* and *methodological sheets* (Michaliszyn-Gabryś et al., 2024) or are not structured for direct comparison between two technological options within the same actor (Naghshineh et al., 2020; Sanchez et al., 2023). As identified by Caruso et al. (2022), this gap presents a significant challenge for organisations using the S-LCA as a decision-making tool to drive internal innovation by evaluating social impacts of technology implementation. To address these, we propose a methodological complement to the indicator selection and impact assessment procedures within Type I S-LCA to support direct comparisons of internal technological transitions. These by applying (i) a comprehensive strategy for selecting social impact categories and subcategories through a rigorous Social Hotspot Analysis; (ii) a conditional score adjustment mechanism to the impact assessment of subcategories using qualitative inputs gathered through targeted stakeholder engagement. Thus, it contributes to the ongoing discourse on standardisation in S-LCA by offering a replicable strategy for incorporating qualitative organisational changes into a robust and comparable impact assessment system. This structured yet adaptable extension to account for internal transitions enhances the resolution and applicability of Type I S-LCA, especially in technology-driven sectors, retaining the core elements from the *guidelines* (see section S1). Additionally, there is a lack of S-LCA studies addressing emerging technologies such as AI-driven advanced laser-based manufacturing. These novel technologies introduce new forms of human-machine interaction and operational transformation that remain unexplored from a social life-cycle perspective (Jahanmahin et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2024; Dhanda et al., 2025).

In summary, while current S-LCA applications remain limited in capturing internal technological changes, this paper proposes a complement to the *guidelines* for Type I S-LCA that integrates for the screening of subcategories and conditional scoring strategies, applied for the first time to an AI-driven laser technology within the aerospace manufacturing sector, representing a novel contribution to S-LCA, aerospace research, and emerging technologies. Accordingly, Section 2 outlines the methods, describing the new strategy for hotspot assessment and the sensitivity analysis; and Section 3 examines its application in an aeronautics manufacturing case study.

2. methods

The proposed methodological contribution specifically extends the Type I grounded in ISO 14075:2024 (BSI and ISO 2024) and UNEP 2020 (UNEP, 2020), consisting of four key phases: (i) Goal and Scope Definition, (ii) Social Life Cycle Inventory (S-LCI), (iii) S-LCIA, and (iv) Interpretation.

2.1. Goal and scope definition

This section outlines the objective of the social life cycle assessment, defines the study's scope, and presents the context in which the assessment is applied.

2.1.1. Context and technological background

This study focuses on the implementation of laser technology within aeronautics manufacturing, a sector that demands precise processes to ensure structural strength, safety, and performance (Li, 2024). These requirements are embedded within stringent regulatory frameworks. In this context, aircraft components are crafted from advanced materials and produced using specialised techniques (Bhavya et al., 2020). One of the most prominent advanced materials is specific composites reinforced with aramid fibres due to their high strength-to-weight ratio, thermal resistance, and impact absorption capabilities (Kukreja and Panda, 2024), commonly used in fuselage structures (Kausar, 2022). Manufacturing these composite components involves several steps, including lay-up, curing, surface preparation, and bonding (Pansart, 2013). One of the most critical concerns is surface preparation, since this step ensures optimal adhesion between composite materials and any subsequent coatings or bonding agents (Rider et al., 2018). This case study highlights challenges with traditional surface treatments like sanding (Fig. 1(A)). These methods depend on manual labour, leading to inconsistent quality, health risks from airborne particles and longer production times. A more precise, repeatable, and sustainable solution is needed to boost manufacturing efficiency and worker safety in aeronautics (Pop et al., 2023).

A novel laser-based manufacturing system was proposed to address this challenge. It introduces ultrashort pulse laser (USPL) as an advanced alternative to conventional methods. This technology enables precise surface microstructuring, significantly enhancing adhesion and eliminating the need for sanding (). A central innovation of this process lies in its integrated cyber-physical system architecture, which is schematically represented in Fig. 1(B). The architecture has two domains: physical and digital. In the physical domain, the laser is generated, amplified, and routed via a polarisation-maintaining optical fibre to the beam delivery module, which directs the beam into configurations like Direct Laser Interference Patterning or Direct Writing. The beam then moves through modules including beam metrology, dynamic shaping, and scanning optics, which adapt it for surface structuring. The laser interacts with the working surface via a configurable motion manipulator (Pandolfi et al., 2025). The architecture supports a Zero-Defect Manufacturing strategy through a continuous data loop between the physical and digital layers. Sensors in the beam metrology, shaping, and motion systems generate real-time data on laser characteristics, stability, and accuracy. This data is processed by modules for readout, optimisation, and control, coordinated by the master controller, which uses AI models to dynamically adjust laser parameters, beam trajectories, and motion paths (Blanco-Filgueira et al., 2025).

2.1.2. Goal definition

The primary objective of this assessment is to evaluate the social implications of adopting USPL texturing for surface preparation on Kevlar composite aircraft fairing components through an S-LCA. Our study aims to evaluate socio-economic changes from adopting these new technologies, not just the sector's social performance.

Fig. 1. Surface treatment, Manual sanding (A) and AI-driven Laser, including the Conceptual representation of the system (B).

2.1.3. Functional unit

The following functional unit (FU) was defined for communication purposes: One aircraft fairing component made of Kevlar composite, manufactured and delivered for installation from Spain. The FU definition in LCA facilitates effective comparisons of product systems by focusing on unit-level processes and their environmental impacts. However, the FU was not considered for the final assessment, as this approach is less applicable to S-LCA because companies, rather than specific processes, have a greater influence on social impacts (UNEP, 2020; Borri et al., 2024). Consequently, while similar industrial processes may result in comparable environmental impacts, the social impacts can vary significantly based on the manufacturer's local characteristics, which are not captured by unit-level process data (Singh and Gupta, 2018).

2.1.4. System boundaries

The system boundaries are presented in Fig. 2. In this process, the aircraft component is manufactured in Spain, where the sequence of operations includes material preparation, lay-up using epoxy adhesives, curing, surface treatment, and painting. Two scenarios are evaluated for the surface treatment stage. *Case 1* represents the manual sanding steps to prepare composite surfaces (Surface Cleaning and Conditioning). *Case 2* introduces new technologies, replacing manual sanding with USPL. It maintains the same general process flow as Case 1, with USPL directly substituting the sanding in the surface conditioning steps after Operation 13. No additional process steps are altered by this substitution, ensuring comparability while isolating the social impacts attributable to the technology replacement. The S-LCA focused on manufacturing, excluding raw material extraction, upstream material production, the use phase, and the end-of-life. This scope was chosen because feedstocks

and materials are complex, multi-tiered intermediate products, making site-specific data infeasible. The use phase and end-of-life were excluded because they fall outside the project's scope. The aircraft components are then provided to another company for the manufacturing of aeroplanes, which is considered a consumer. For new technologies, there is a consortium comprising 16 organisations based in Europe (OPeraTIC Consortium, 2022).

2.1.5. Stakeholder categories

This study also adhered to the five stakeholders outlined in the S-LCA guidelines: Workers, Local Communities, Value Chain Actors, Consumers, and Society. Children are not considered in this S-LCA because the assessment focuses on industrial manufacturing settings, where direct child involvement is not a relevant social concern based on the scope defined by the *methodological sheets*. This is distinct from the *child labour* subcategory under Workers. The stakeholder group 'Children' encompasses subcategories such as *Education provided in the local community*, *Health issues for children as consumers*, and *children concerns regarding marketing practices*, none of which apply to the assessed companies. However, education initiatives in the local community have already been evaluated regarding access to immaterial resources.

2.1.6. Impact categories, subcategories, and indicators

This study follows the framework of impact categories and subcategories outlined in the *guidelines*. While the *methodological sheets* primarily focus on the subcategories relevant to each stakeholder, the study also acknowledges the main social impact categories: *Human Rights*, *Working Conditions*, *Health and Safety*, *Socioeconomic Repercussions*, and *Governance*. The selection of subcategories was based on the results of the hotspot assessment. While no additional subcategories

Fig. 2. Operation-level value chain & stakeholder map.

were proposed, some minor modifications were made to adjust them to the case. The indicators used to evaluate each subcategory are based on the references provided in the *methodological sheets* and encompass

qualitative, semi-quantitative, and quantitative data. A comprehensive overview of the selected subcategories, relevant reference frameworks and the state of the art is provided in [Tables S1.1 and S1.2](#). Subcategories

Fig. 3. Subcategory consideration decision tree.

and indicators are presented in Table S2.

2.1.7. Hotspot assessment

All subcategories listed in the *methodological sheets* for the mentioned stakeholders were initially considered. A hotspot assessment was conducted to identify the relevant subcategories for the case, resulting in 21 social impact subcategories. The goal of this step was to determine the most significant social impact subcategories. Generally, this assessment is based entirely on generic indicators from recognised secondary sources and S-LCA databases (Tables S3.1 and S3.2). For this study, the various secondary sources are presented in Table S2, organised by impact social subcategory, as well as the Social Hotspots Database (SHDB) (Benoit-Norris et al., 2012). However, because many indicators were either sector-specific or national, their ability to reflect site-specific realities was limited. To address this limitation, we developed a new structured screening framework (Fig. 3) that combines quantitative and qualitative criteria to inform the inclusion or exclusion of subcategories.

This decision-making flowchart incorporated qualitative insights, including (i.) A review of expected social impacts from the introduction of advanced manufacturing technologies, with a focus on risks and opportunities identified in similar industrial settings (from Table S2, see ‘Expected social impacts’ row); (ii.) Sustainability and activity reports from companies across the value chain; (iii.) Cross-checks with databases such as the Business & Human Rights Resource Centre (BHRRC, 2024); (iv.) Screening of international and local media, NGO reports, and governmental findings related to specific organisations; (v.) A review of the state of the art regarding the subcategories. These are presented in Section S3: Qualitative specific assessment per company. A full operational description of Q1–Q5 criteria, inclusion thresholds, decision rationale, and the final decision on the selection of social impact subcategories is given in Table S3.3.

2.2. S-LCI

The S-LCI was structured into four tiers (Fig. 4), each representing a different degree of data availability and specificity. Tier 0 actors, which include upstream suppliers and final consumers, were not accessible in this study and were excluded due to limited traceability and a lack of publicly available information. Tier 1 includes eleven companies that supply materials for surface treatment and aircraft manufacturing. The inventory data at this level has been supplemented with publicly

available secondary information to enhance the robustness. All companies underwent screening through the Business & Human Rights Resource Centre (BHRRC, 2024), and further verification was conducted using sustainability reports, codes of conduct, company websites, national and international news outlets, and official reports from governmental and non-governmental sources. Tier 2 consists of thirteen companies within the project consortium, like Tier 1, but with the added advantage of continuous engagement and validation. Tier 3 refers to the central company directly implementing the evaluated technologies. At this level, detailed primary data were collected through ongoing communication, and a comprehensive questionnaire was designed specifically for this case study, developed in accordance with methodological guidelines and comprising nearly 100 questions across all selected subcategories. Although the responses remain confidential, the questionnaire template is provided in Section S4.

To ensure consistency, a pedigree matrix was developed. This matrix evaluates data quality using four dimensions: source reliability, completeness, temporal conformance, and scope alignment (Table S5). Each score was adjusted by a quality factor ranging from 0 to 1. High-quality data was multiplied by 1, while lower-quality data was proportionally downweighted. This approach allowed all relevant data to contribute to the evaluation while minimising the bias that could arise from direct exclusion. This multi-tiered strategy strikes a balance between breadth and depth, allowing for a nuanced assessment of social performance.

2.3. S-LCIA

A multi-level valuation scale method is used to interpret inventory analysis results by assigning semiquantitative intensity scores to different impact levels. The impacts from 21 specific subcategories were then grouped into five broader social impact categories. Finally, the results were weighted to create a single index representing the system’s overall social performance.

2.3.1. Characterisation methods

The characterisation phase in this study employed a structured approach to translate inventory data into interpretable social performance results. This was achieved using a reference scale system that aligns with the guidelines. The developed indicators utilised a five-point valuation scale, ranging from -2 (indicating worst performance) to +2

Fig. 4. Life cycle diagram.

(indicating ideal performance), with 0 as the reference point (Sigcha et al., 2024; Luna Ostos et al., 2024). This reference point corresponds to European average values or baseline regulatory expectations (see Table S2). For each social impact subcategory, a set of generic and specific indicators is proposed, based on the available data. Generic indicators, used in Tiers 1 and Tier 2, were normalised through non-linear transformations based on the reference scale. In contrast, the specific indicators used in Tier 3 were mainly qualitative, aligning with the scope aim presented in the *methodological sheet*. Social data are not always subject to open-disclosure policies, resulting in incomplete data for S-LCA analyses (Zamagni et al., 2015). Missing data (2.8% of the inventory) were conservatively scored as 0 for Tier 1. In this context, a score of 0 reflects the absence of evidence to justify deviation from the benchmark, rather than an assumption of negative performance. Assigning negative scores to missing data, e.g., -2 (Luna Ostos et al., 2024), would introduce a normative bias by conflating data availability

with social performance, which may not reflect actual conditions. This is acceptable specifically for this study because it is further supported by the system context, as Tier 1 actors operate within the aerospace sector in highly regulated environments (EU/USA), where compliance with minimum legal and social standards is expected. Additionally, due diligence processes are in place at the main company level. On the other hand, the missing data were consistent across both scenarios, ensuring that comparative results are not affected. Individual actor scores were calculated independently. Then, the three groups (suppliers, main company, and consumer) were initially aggregated equally to determine the final score for each subcategory.

The initial scores derived from generic indicators in Tiers 1 and 2 were adjusted when additional evidence contradicted the generic risk level. For instance, while a country-level score for *freedom of association* might indicate systemic risks at -1, if a particular company was found to actively uphold strong labour rights policies and demonstrate a

Fig. 5. Heatmap of Social Subcategories per Company. Main¹: Main company (Manual Sanding); Main²: Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 0.1$); Main³: Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 0.5$); Main⁴: Main Company (USPL, $\alpha = 1$); OPeraTIC consortium: Companies J to V.

proactive stance, the score was adjusted to +1. Qualitative criteria guided these modifications, since available information was heterogeneous, nuanced, or incomplete. In parallel, the Tier 3 assessment is summarised in Table S6.1, which is based on the specific indicator and the questionnaire. These were subsequently adjusted based on their quality, as explained in the S-LCI using the pedigree Matrix. The Quality Weighting Factors are presented in Table S6.2, and the final scores per social impact subcategory are presented in Fig. 5. The data, both unadjusted and adjusted, are shown in Tables S6.3 and S6.4, respectively.

2.3.2. Sensitivity analysis

Benchmark-based S-LCA translates qualitative social dynamics into discretised ordinal performance levels (Sigcha et al., 2024; Luna Ostos et al., 2024). To introduce contextual flexibility within these fixed scales, some studies have employed adjustment strategies, typically applying a +1 level shift to reflect additional considerations not captured in the original indicator definition (Osorio-Tejada et al., 2022). However, they are generally asymmetric and assume that contextual evidence warrants a full discrete level change. In early-stage technological assessments, however, the magnitude of social effect may be uncertain and may not justify an immediate categorical shift. Conditionals were created as part of the designated indicators within an adjustment architecture to provide additional positive or negative values based on contextual evidence, rather than prescribing a fixed modifier (e.g., +1). For instance, if increased productivity occurred without a corresponding wage adjustment or social compensation, a negative correction ($-a$) was applied; if upskilling was required and adequately compensated, a positive correction ($+a$) was granted. This approach introduced the parameter a to simulate varying impact intensity within the -2 to $+2$ benchmark scale, representing decremental/incremental shifts (up to one level). The analysis was conducted with three magnitudes (± 0.1 , ± 0.5 , and ± 1.0) to represent minor, moderate, and a full one-level shift, enabling structured exploration of system responsiveness within the benchmark scale. The initial sensitivity analysis assessed the social impact of adopting USPL under specific conditions, while the manual sanding scenario was kept constant. Refer to Table S2: 'Other considerations' row for the complete list of conditionals per social impact subcategory.

To standardise the analysis and ensure consistency across scenarios, a uniform a -value was applied to all conditionals and subcategories within each scenario. Although this assumes equal magnitude of adjustment across subcategories, despite differences in their real-world contexts, it facilitates a controlled sensitivity sweep to evaluate how social scores respond to incremental increases/decreases in assumed impact intensity. In practice, various conditionals (e.g., wage adjustment versus surveillance) might differ in real-world effect magnitude; however, calibrating differentiated effect sizes would require a separate elicitation process beyond the scope of this study. This simplification enables the illustration of the methodological responsiveness and consistency under clearly defined boundary assumptions. These effects are illustrated in Fig. 6, which compares social performance scores between the manual sanding and USPL. This sensitivity analysis directly addresses the methodological gap identified in S-LCA, its limited capacity to detect social impacts arising from internal technological changes without altering supply chain actors. Simulating conditional variations in impact intensity offers a practical way to improve the responsiveness of Type I S-LCA frameworks and to establish a structured methodological basis for future calibration of subcategory-specific effect magnitudes.

The analysis combines conditional scoring adjustments with life cycle stage weighting scenarios to explore how different assumptions affect the final social impact results. The second sensitivity analysis was conducted after the aggregation step to assess how altering the relative importance of various life-cycle stages affected the final social performance scores. Due to data limitations and the lack of a normalising activity variable, the analysis employed a stakeholder-weighted scheme

reflecting three production phases: material manufacturing, component manufacturing, and final assembly. These were represented in the evaluation as Suppliers, Main Company, and Consumers, respectively, serving as proxies for the stages within the system boundary. The default setup assigned equal weights (1/3 each), while several alternative distributions were tested to explore different emphasis scenarios.

2.3.3. Weighting and aggregation

To synthesise the social impact scores into a composite Social Performance Index (SPI), we applied a weighting structure aligned with the reference framework presented in Table S1.2. The aggregation process incorporated the judgment of experts selected to represent the five stakeholder groups. Each participant was selected based on their domain expertise, which aligned with the stakeholder group they represented. The composition of the expert pool is presented in Table S6.5, comprising up to 31 representatives. To derive the relative weights, we employed the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) (Saaty, 1987). The survey is presented in Section S6: Worker Survey (example). In cases where the consistency ratio exceeded the threshold of 0.2, which is considered acceptable in group-based AHP applications involving complex multi-criteria judgments (Dolan, 2008), an iterative correction was applied by using Harker's method, implemented via the *ahpsurvey* package in R (Cho, 2019). Final aggregation of responses was conducted using the geometric mean (Zira et al., 2020). The derived weights were used to aggregate the scores from individual subcategories into categories, ultimately resulting in a single SPI per scenario, as illustrated in Fig. 7 for the default weighted scheme. In contrast, Fig. 8(A) visualises the variability in SPI outcomes across different life-cycle-stage weighting configurations, and Fig. 8(B) displays the improvement offered by USPL over Manual Sanding. This result indicates that although subcategory scores varied across emphasis conditions, the overall trends remained consistent, demonstrating directional stability of comparative outcomes across assumptions with different shift magnitudes. These final weights and the aggregation structure are presented in Section S6: AHP (Tables S6.6-S6.14). The priority indexes are presented in Table S6.15.

2.4. Interpretation

This section synthesises the robustness of findings through completeness, consistency, and sensitivity checks, providing a transparent account of the methodological and data-related assumptions underlying the results.

2.4.1. Completeness check

Tier 1 and Tier 3 data were compiled for each company, with no subcategory or stakeholder group excluded. Although complete, excluding downstream impacts, especially use-phase effects, may limit broader representativeness. This was necessary due to the scope and confidentiality.

2.4.2. Consistency check

To ensure methodological consistency, we followed the *guidelines*. We avoided double-counting by aligning subcategories with the *methodological sheets'* recommendations. We acknowledge a score dilution effect due to varying data quality, which defaults to zero when no information is available from secondary sources. On the other hand, adjusting scores based on company disclosures added complexity. Although we used structured review criteria, the qualitative and heterogeneous nature of the reports, which varied mainly in their adherence to voluntary frameworks such as GRI, introduced subjectivity, a significant limitation of the study.

2.4.3. Sensitivity and data quality check

The pedigree matrix for Tier 1 data showed several subcategories with lower data quality, including Feedback Mechanisms, Fair

Fig. 6. Social performance by subcategory.

Fig. 7. Social Performance by category and SPI.

Competition, Local Employment, Equal Opportunities/Discrimination, Wealth Distribution, and Consumer Privacy. In contrast, subcategories like Promoting Social Responsibility, Supplier Relationship, and Public Commitment to Sustainability Issues faced data quality challenges due to insufficient disclosure by specific companies (Table S6.2).

2.4.4. Assumptions and limitations

When no secondary data or adverse reports were available, subcategories were scored at zero (0) instead of assuming positive or negative performance. For three companies with limited public disclosures, this assumption was justified, as they operate in regulated environments (the EU or the USA), where minimal legal compliance is presumed, and due diligence is placed by the main company. Nevertheless, this assumption may underestimate potential risks associated with incomplete disclosure, which is recognised as a limitation of the study. Additionally, for subcategories where improvements are associated with anticipated operational changes (e.g., reductions in airborne particulates or automation-related adjustments), the resulting scores reflect evidence-informed projections within the defined system boundaries rather than empirically measured post-implementation outcomes. It is important to note that the assessment reflects short-to mid-term operational conditions; therefore, longer-term social dynamics associated with technological adoption are not captured within the current system boundary.

3. Results and discussion

This case study examines a transition in which the primary actors remain essentially unchanged but undergo significant technological or organisational changes. Conditional scoring (a-values) in Tier 3

qualitative inputs helps capture subtler shifts in social performance that actor-based assessments may miss. Fig. 6 visualises these dynamics and provides a granular comparison of social impact subcategories across the two cases. This suggests that the proposed approach contributes to addressing the gap in standard S-LCA practice, where internal technological innovations would otherwise go unnoticed due to reliance on static value chain configurations.

The Workers stakeholder group indicates positive shifts across several subcategories. An improvement in the Fair Salary is anticipated, with internal reporting indicating above-average wages and expected increases tied to upskilling requirements for the new technology, in accordance with Naghshineh et al. (2020). Health and Safety also support improvements due to their direct link to the enhanced working conditions resulting from the automation (Pandolfi et al., 2025). Notably, this was one of the few subcategories to receive the highest positive modifier (+2a) due to the potential reduction in hazardous dust exposure and improvement in ergonomics. Even if the laser process may generate process-specific fumes from epoxy resin ablation, the system is designed with local extraction, which is not present in the manual sanding baseline. Thus, a reduced worker exposure to airborne is indeed identified. For Working Hours, even if the technology reduces processing time, this improvement does not translate into shorter working hours or increased flexibility for employees, since this is defined as a contractual condition, reflecting the situation stated by Dachs (2018). Social Benefits/Security and Freedom of Association showed no performance shift; while the company complies with legal requirements, no proactive measures are planned to enhance benefits or union engagement. Equal Opportunities/Discrimination showed a proactive score, driven by inclusive policies and training. Even when Singh and Gupta (2018) state that new technologies in manufacturing may favour conditions that lead to

Fig. 8. Sensitivity Analysis of Social Performance Scores by Life Cycle Stage Weighting and α -Values (A), and Improvement over Manual Sanding (B). C: Consumer; M: Main Company; S: Suppliers.

employment inequalities; in this case study, these technologies are not expected to introduce structural imbalances.

In *Access to Material Resources* for Local Communities, according to Michaliszyn-Gabryś et al. (2024), new technologies may increase demand for specific critical resources needed for the systems; however, given the quantities and lifespans of the equipment, this is expected to be marginal. The transition to USPL is reported to improve resource efficiency, as solar panels offset increased electricity demand from the laser process. Internal efficiency gains may not benefit the local community, even as they ease utility strain and promote sustainability. No direct infrastructure or community resource development is involved. *Safe and Healthy Living Conditions* may benefit from USPL implementation, as its expected to reduce airborne particulates, dust, and chemical residues from local emissions. However, these benefits haven't been empirically measured in communities, and the positive impact is based on expected rather than verified performance. The $+\alpha$ score is a qualified assumption based on process comparisons and should be treated cautiously. Future studies should include direct environmental or health monitoring near the production site to validate these projected benefits. For *Local Employment*, it's essential to note that automation is often associated with concerns about job displacement (Dachs, 2018; Singh and Gupta, 2018); however, the data indicate that the implemented changes would improve workers' conditions rather than worsen them. On the other hand, new positions are expected to emerge due to the technology's operational demands, while existing local hiring agreements remain

intact, and no outsourcing has been reported. These findings align with those of Sanchez et al. (2023), who suggest that new technologies can directly benefit local communities by creating job opportunities. This assessment reflects short-to medium-term organisational planning within the defined system boundary; long-term automation dynamics or indirect supplier-level employment effects were not within the scope.

In *Fair Competition*, Michaliszyn-Gabryś et al. (2024) noted that the new technologies could influence competition by giving early adopters a significant advantage, potentially creating disparities. There is no sign that USPL leads to exclusive partnerships or vendor lock-in. Instead, the main company mentioned that it may encourage wider access by advocating for better compliance and quality standards across the supply chain. In the case of *Promoting Social Responsibility*, the laser implementation inherently raises occupational health and environmental standards, which extend to the supply chain. For *Supplier relationships*, while the structural relationship remains intact, adopting USPL requires new qualifications and certifications. This promotes technological adaptation and nurtures long-term partnerships focused on knowledge exchange and innovation, even if not fully institutionalised. *Respect of Intellectual Property Rights* remained unchanged. The technology introduces proprietary processes and technical know-how, but without a parallel enhancement in IP governance. While the new technology may ultimately enhance value creation, it is currently expected to favour a subset of suppliers, those capable of quickly adapting to the technical requirements. This situation might create a risk of temporary market

polarisation, in which less-resourced suppliers are excluded from new business opportunities, even if the company's pricing strategy aims to remain balanced. This aligns with [Naghshineh et al. \(2021\)](#), who mentioned that implementing new manufacturing technologies may result in a reconfiguration of the supply chain. However, no further evidence supported this statement, so *Wealth Distribution* did not receive a modifier based on the conditionals.

For the *Health and Safety of Consumers*, its anticipated contribution to product integrity and reliability is substantial. USPL offers greater precision, lower material degradation, and more consistent outcomes compared to manual sanding ([Pandolfi et al., 2025](#)). These potential improvements contribute indirectly to enhanced consumer safety, particularly in aeronautical applications where tolerances are incredibly tight. Regarding *Transparency*, it is also expected to improve; the introduction of USPL has prompted increased documentation, technical reporting, and contractual communication between the company and its clients. On the other hand, the company has outlined plans to integrate a dedicated *feedback Mechanism* system specifically to monitor performance and issues arising from the new technology. Although this system is not yet implemented, the structured approach and intent justify the adjustment $+a$, as they reflect a shift toward more proactive consumer engagement. According to [Niermann et al. \(2023\)](#), *consumer privacy* is a critical consideration in the adoption of new technologies, but in this case, it does not significantly alter data flows, remaining neutral in this assessment. Protection mechanisms are already in place and continue to operate under the new process.

The *public commitment to Sustainability Issues for Society* received an $+a$ adjustment. Based on [Naghshineh et al. \(2021\)](#) and [Niermann et al. \(2023\)](#), USPL integration potentially advances sustainability, especially in environmental and health aspects. The company promotes the project, highlighting laser technology that reduces waste. While not yet quantified, the technology's alignment with goals justifies a positive outlook. The *contribution to economic development* was estimated using national labour productivity data. This indicator does not rely on conditionals; however, the benefits from USPL are increased productivity through process efficiency. The *Technology Development* is associated with an improvement due to a reported increase in the company's R&D investment associated with the USPL implementation.

Overall, the potential improvements observed in 14 of 21 subcategories reflect the cumulative effect of occupational safety gains, process efficiency improvements, and strengthened governance-related practices associated with USPL implementation. No evidence-supported negative directional conditionals were substantiated within the defined system boundary. Thus, while the direction of change remained consistent across all tested perturbation magnitudes, these results should be interpreted as evidence-informed directional tendencies rather than empirically calibrated effect sizes, and are not predictive of the final impact magnitudes. This is due to the technology's early-stage deployment.

As shown in [Fig. 7](#), the aggregation of subcategories into impact categories now provides a basis for interpreting broader category-level trends. *Working Conditions* showed an expected positive shift under the USPL scenario, with a steady rise across a -values. This reflects the technological change's occupational nature and its focus on labour safety and efficiency. However, this shouldn't be observed as a definitive impact measure, as the same a -correction was used across all subcategories. In practice, social improvements, especially those related to worker well-being, may require a larger magnitude for the conditionals than others, which isn't captured by the uniform sensitivity design. This simplification, although necessary for structured analysis, may obscure the nuanced relevance of impacts at the worker level compared to other stakeholder domains.

The *Human Rights* category remained unchanged across all scenarios. This stability is directly linked to its representation by a single subcategory, *Equal Opportunities/Discrimination*, which was unaffected by the introduction of USPL. Because there are no risks in this industrial setting,

human rights were not a significant target for impact, despite their substantial weight in the overall analysis. Thus, even high-priority categories may show no visible effect if they are not connected to the specific intervention.

The *Governance and Socioeconomic Repercussions* categories showed potential improvement. These expected gains indicate how adopting advanced technologies aligns with regulatory best practices and fosters innovation within the value chain. The upward trends in these categories are consistent with the notion that targeted technological changes can facilitate broader compliance and strategic economic benefits. Notably, stability in some governance indicators indicates institutional maturity, while changes in socioeconomic metrics suggest tangible, though incremental, systemic development.

The *Heritage and Communities* category showed a likelihood of improvement, with increasing scores across all a -values. Although this category had a lower weight in the overall assessment, its responsiveness to the introduction of cleaner, more efficient processes underscores the importance of localised and environmental-social intersections.

The SPI indicates a positive social outcome across scenarios. While useful for high-level comparisons, it overlooks differences in how categories respond to change. Though it simplifies outcomes for communication and screening, it complements detailed impact insights, creating a balanced depth of decision-support tools. As shown in [Fig. 8](#), the SPIs are robust across various weightings and life cycle stages. This sensitivity analysis tested different focus areas in the supply chain, material manufacturing, component manufacturing, and final assembly, and found that the USPL consistently outperformed manual sanding, regardless of a -values or weights. This indicates robustness under the tested assumptions and shows that conditional scoring sensitivity enhances S-LCA's ability to detect social performance changes driven by technological shifts.

This assessment's outcomes offer practical insights for diverse audiences. Policymakers can use the SPI to synthesise complex social data and identify socially beneficial innovations. As a planning tool, it can guide decisions on emerging tech and support Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) strategies, but requires detailed category-level data to avoid masking negative impacts. The framework could also underpin future real-time S-LCA implementations in digitally enabled production systems. For industry decision-makers, the rising SPI trend shows AI-driven USPL as a socially progressive alternative to traditional methods. Its adoption should be part of broader strategies, including stakeholder engagement and social impact monitoring, to enhance benefits throughout the product lifecycle. Methodologically, using a single a -value across categories needs refinement—future S-LCA should assign different a -values based on category sensitivity or stakeholder context to improve accuracy and credibility.

4. Conclusions

This study addressed a key gap in S-LCA: its limited capacity to identify the social impacts of internal technological changes that don't alter supply chains. We developed and tested a sensitivity-based approach that combines conditional scoring with stakeholder inputs. Key achievements include: (i) a hotspot assessment framework for selecting relevant social subcategories, and (ii) a conditional scoring (a -value) approach to explore potential impact variations from technological changes within organisations. The case study on USPL in aeronautics manufacturing proved the framework's applicability and effectiveness under defined sensitivity conditions. Results indicate potential social improvements across 14 of 21 subcategories, especially in Working Conditions, Governance, and Socioeconomic Repercussions, highlighting USPL as a potential socially progressive alternative to manual sanding. This is the first S-LCA to assess a system with USPL, AI, and robotics, an emerging industrial setup with strategic importance. These findings improve S-LCA by offering a practical method to incorporate internal changes into impact assessments, supporting socially

responsible innovation. Future work should refine the calibration of conditional adjustments and test this approach across different industrial contexts to broaden validation.

Consent to participate

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Consent to publish

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Ricardo Mejía-Marchena: Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Methodology, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **José Osorio-Tejada:** Data curation, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Software, Supervision, Validation, Writing – review & editing. **Alejandro Domínguez-Núñez:** Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Volker Hessel:** Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Investigation, Project administration, Resources, Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.clrc.2026.100448>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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